

Predictors of irrational beliefs and behaviours: A critical perspective

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The purpose of this paper is to review the key individual and social predictors of irrational beliefs and behaviours. Initially, the definition of logic and irrationality was attempted, and the various approaches that exist in this regard, philosophical and psychological. Rational Emotional Behaviour Therapy (REBT) has dealt extensively with the causes and consequences of irrational beliefs. The review highlighted some individual predictors, such as anger, hostility, and demandingness. At the same time, irrational beliefs are systematically associated with mental difficulties and disorders such as posttraumatic stress, addictions, and anxiety disorders. Social factors do not seem to have been adequately studied or are only briefly referenced. Also, the important role of emotions and the possible positive effects of some irrational beliefs were highlighted. The results of the review are discussed based on a more complete understanding of the causes and consequences of irrational beliefs and behaviours.

Keywords: behaviours; irrational beliefs; mental disorders; perspective; rational emotional behaviour therapy

Logic and irrationality are not easy to define, and in trying to define them, different theorists often set different criteria. If we consider logic an attempt at understanding, we understand that this involves many subjective and interpretive elements. According to Weber (1947), any attempt at interpretive understanding involves two elements: the emotional and the rational one. In this case, the objectives of understanding are either logical or mathematical sentences, or actions involving identifiable ends and means (Toth, 2013).

According to the methodological approach, logic is the basic principle and condition for any explanation and interpretation. As long as they are intentional, all actions are logical. Logic is the beginning behind all theoretical and interpretive models (e.g., Dow & Mises, 1958; Popper, 1985, p. 357). According to the same approach, irrationality results from a lack of data and information or precisely because this data and information are not relevant to understanding these phenomena (e.g., Boudon, 2003; Gibbs & Coleman, 1990; Weber, 1947). For the ontological approach, on the other hand, the criteria of logic are set each time by the standards set by the experts to assess the appropriateness of the actions or beliefs. (e.g., Stewart & Pareto, 1964). Ignorance, therefore, is a characteristic that has meaning for actions, beliefs, cultures, or various social categories. Irrationality exists as a distinct feature of the human psyche, and universal criteria can be defined for separating actions and beliefs into logical and irrational. Phenomena such as pious desires, weak will, and self-deception can be considered illogical (Davidson, 2004; Elster, 1983).

Most of the psychological approaches to irrationality are part of this ontological approach. In early childhood, people develop certain beliefs about themselves, other people, and their world. People's most central or core beliefs are perceptions so fundamental and profound that they often do not even express themselves. These ideas are treated by the individual as absolute truths and as the way things 'are'. There are several levels of cognitive structures. Core beliefs are the most fundamental level of belief and are spherical, rigid, and supernatural. Automatic thoughts, words, or images that pass through a person's mind are associated with a particular situation and can be considered an additional superficial level of knowledge. There is the category of intermediate beliefs between these two levels of knowledge, which often consist of unexpressed attitudes, rules, and assumptions. These beliefs affect how a person sees a situation, affecting how he thinks, feels, and behaves (Beck, 2010).

Rational emotional behaviour therapy (REBT) theory is known for irrational beliefs as the root cause of our psychological problems (Ellis et al., 2009). The theory was first introduced as rational therapy (RT) until later; the significance of the effects on emotions was recognised and took its final form when irrational beliefs were considered the root causes of dysfunctional emotions and concussions. This theory significantly contributed to the formation of the popular CBT and was its forerunner. Beliefs, according to Ellis, fall into four main categories: (a) demands, beliefs that represent events, situations; (b) and their consequences as terrible and awful; (c) beliefs that suggest low tolerance for frustration; (d) and beliefs that are suggestive of the value and acceptance of ourselves (David et al., 2010).

The roots of all cognitive therapies are also found in ancient philosophers, mainly Epictetus, who proclaimed that 'men are not disturbed by things, but by the view which they take of them'. Although irrational beliefs and thoughts have been repeatedly linked to negative emotions, the mechanism by which this happens has not been fully understood. (Turner, 2016; Vĭsla et al., 2016). In recent literatures (e.g., Collard et al., 2016; Gagani et al., 2016), there are references to the possible positive consequences of certain irrational beliefs. The basic idea is not new (Taylor & Brown, 1988). The main argument is that positive illusions do not always lead to feelings of subjective discomfort but may sometimes be associated with the development of adaptive mechanisms at the behavioural, cognitive, and emotional levels. There are similar reports of negative and irrational feelings, such as anger and fear, which can be logical if we understand the purpose they perform as an appropriate reaction to a corresponding stimulus (Pilao et al., 2016; Relojo, 2015).

This article aims to attempt a review of the key individual and social predictors of irrational behaviours and beliefs. In addition, the article aims to capture the relationship between irrational beliefs and behaviours with mental health difficulties.

Predictive factors of irrational behaviours and thoughts

A literature review shows that there are more theoretical and research references to irrational beliefs than to irrational behaviours. There is also a plethora of references to individual factors while social factors are under-represented or reported in addition or covertly. An additional observation concerns the plethora of studies relating to the association of specific mental disorders and irrational beliefs. With regard to individual factors, anger and hostility combined with irrational beliefs, such as intolerance of rules frustration, intolerance of work frustration, demands fairness, and self-downing, have been linked to direct and

indirect aggressive behaviour in adolescents. Studies like this shed light on the relationship between cognition and behaviour and emotions and behaviour (Fives et al., 2011).

Recent research links the level of rational beliefs with self-doubt (Balkis & Duru, 2018). In particular, the results show that both self-downing and rational beliefs have a direct and interactive effect on self-doubt. Self-doubt also mediates the relationship between self-downing and procrastination. More specifically, it is suggested that the indirect effect of self-downing on procrastination via self-doubt mediation may vary depending on the level of rational beliefs. Results specifically confirm the theoretical link between self-downing, self-doubt, and procrastination (Ellis & Knaus, 1977; Ferrari et al., 1995).

A different but interesting perspective presents a study proposing an evolutionary explanation for irrational behaviour. In the context of a simple binary choice model, it shows that irrational attitudes are necessary for evolution in stochastic environments. In addition, it seems that there is a respectable degree of irrationality in humans, which also depends on the randomness of the population. In this process, mutation provides the important link between rational and irrational attitudes and the diversity in evolution (Brennan et al., 2018). In this context, it is emphasised that because the definition of 'rationality' depends on a particular environment, rational attitudes could change when the environment changes. As a result, irrational behaviour is necessary to provide robustness for population growth. Furthermore, it has been shown that there is an evolutionarily determined degree of irrationality in the whole population. More unstable environments imply more irrational attitudes in the population and more new entries over time (e.g., McKenzie et al., 2004)

The relationship between worry and irrational beliefs has been supported by Lorcher (2003), while emphasising the importance of feeling loved, acknowledged, the importance of the past as a determining factor for the present, and the fact that we tend to get upset when things do not go the way we want them to. These findings support the cognitive model of Kelly and Miller (1999) and confirm even earlier studies that supported the positive correlation of irrational beliefs with unpleasant experiences.

A meta-analysis of the relationship between irrational beliefs and psychological distress (Oltean & David, 2018) revealed that the association between rational beliefs and distress is robust for a wide range of emotional problems. Therefore, rational beliefs can act as protective factors against distress. The findings confirm that the type of rational beliefs is an important factor and suggests that treatment needs to emphasise unconditional acceptance and self-acceptance. The results also seem to have intercultural power, in that the fact that the country is not a significant moderator points out that the relationship between rational beliefs and distress does not vary by culture. However, the generalisation of the result is narrowed because almost all studies were conducted in western countries. Moreover, data showed that the association between rational beliefs and psychological distress is not moderated by age, gender, clinical status, or the participants' irrational beliefs. These might mean that rational beliefs act as a protective factor against psychological disturbances both for males and females, young and old persons, and people affected by mental disorders and those without a mental health diagnosis.

Irrational beliefs and specific mental health difficulties

Regarding specific forms of psychopathology, previous studies by young people experiencing difficulties related to substance abuse or delinquent behaviour show that avoidance and control of emotions collectively suggest a pattern of distorted thinking, ineffective management, or secondary appraisal of situations (Bernard & Joyce, 1984; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). As avoidance indicates the individual's tendency to shun difficult situations, avoidance tendencies could influence possible coping options. By maintaining the conviction that it is best not to work through difficult situations, adolescents who adhere to beliefs about avoidance would probably be induced to consider retreat as a solution to difficult family situations. Control of emotions involves the fatalistic belief that one is unable to control unwanted feelings. It follows that adolescents who hold beliefs about avoidance and the inability to control emotions would be likely to perceive themselves as unable to negotiate or manage situations appraised as difficult (Denoff, 1987).

Further studies have linked irrational beliefs to psychopathology. In the context of investigating the effectiveness of REBT, Hyland et al. (2015) suggest that the presence of general-level irrational beliefs (demandingness beliefs, catastrophising beliefs, low frustration tolerance beliefs, and depreciation beliefs) within an individual's cognitive architecture is an important cognitive vulnerability factor for the development of posttraumatic stress reactions, while the more context-specific variants of these cognitive processes – associated with a person's traumatic experiences – appear to be a stronger

predictor of such psychopathological manifestations. Therefore, no direct effect is usually observed between general-level irrationality and posttraumatic stress symptomatology, but additional factors related to personal experience or emotion that may predict the onset of posttraumatic symptoms are likely to be involved.

In the same context, demandingness beliefs are viewed as the primary irrational belief process and are predicted to give rise to a set of secondary irrational appraisal beliefs that are extreme. These include catastrophising beliefs, which describe the process of evaluating an event in the most extremely negative manner possible, low frustration tolerance beliefs, which involve a person territorially underestimating their own ability to tolerate or cope with the distress of not having their demand met, and depreciation beliefs, which involve a person making overgeneralised, global negative evaluations of the self, others and the world. REBT theory is explicit in claims that demandingness beliefs should affect various states of psychopathology indirectly through catastrophising, low frustration, tolerance, and/or depreciation beliefs (David et al., 2010; Ellis, 1994).

Regarding the above, a study (Hyland et al., 2014) was interested in identifying the organisation of irrational beliefs by investigating the indirect pathways between demandingness beliefs and the various symptom clusters of PTSD. Multiple indirect effects were observed, from demandingness beliefs to intrusions, avoidance, dysphoria, and hyperarousal. In the case of relationships between demandingness beliefs and the intrusions and hyperarousal symptom clusters, respectively, indirect effects were observed for all three secondary irrational belief processes. While in the relationship between demandingness, beliefs, and avoidance symptoms, indirect effects were observed for catastrophising and depreciation beliefs, and in the relationship between demandingness beliefs and dysphoria symptoms, indirect effects were observed for low frustration tolerance and depreciation beliefs. These results are consistent with the predictions of REBT theory (David et al., 2010; Ellis, 1994; Walen et al., 1992) and are generally in line with previous research and studies.

Although the role of irrational beliefs in the development and maintenance of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) has been sufficiently investigated, its exact mechanism or further dimensions are not sufficiently known. Cognitive-behavioural models for OCD suggest that misconceptions about the importance and need to control thoughts lead people with OCD to use overly dysfunctional thought control strategies such as worry and self-punishment. These strategies are thought to back, leading to obsessional symptoms. Jacoby et al. (2016) supports that the use of punishment (but not worry) as a thought control tactic mediated the relationship between dysfunctional beliefs about the importance/control of thoughts and unacceptable obsessions.

We should not omit the psychotic disorders characterised by certain irrational thoughts and taste processes, such as paranoia and hallucinations. Clinical experience often confirms the diagnostic criteria. The existence of these irrational beliefs has been investigated, and while it is first observed (e.g., Owen et al., 2007), it does not seem to be confirmed to the expected degree. Specifically, results suggest that rational thinking is more normal in patients with schizophrenia than usually assumed (Revsbech et al., 2015) and that patients with schizophrenia, despite psychosis, do not perform qualitatively differently from controls in syllogism tests of rationality. However, results may indicate that the observed rationality deficits in schizophrenia (Guttman, 2017), to some extent, reflect deficits in cognitive and neuropsychological functions. However, pre-existing irrational thoughts can lead to paranoid thoughts and more negative perceptions of others than rational beliefs, according to the ABC model. These irrational thoughts seem to persist even after the control of paranoid thoughts. (Soflau & David, 2019). Research such as the above also highlights the need to functionally define concepts such as irrational beliefs and further demonstrates the importance of appropriate diagnostic tests.

The important role of emotion is highlighted by research highlighting emotional intelligence as a stronger predictor of psychopathology than mindfulness and irrational beliefs combined (Petrides et al., 2016). Emotional perceptions stemming from the emotional intelligence trait were stronger predictors of psychopathology than mindfulness and irrational beliefs in a clinical adult sample. The authors suggest that negative emotional self-perceptions are perhaps more fundamental than irrational thinking or lack of awareness in the development of psychopathology. It seems that such self-perceptions lead to psychopathology both directly, but also indirectly, through clouding awareness and fueling irrational thinking.

Finally, the role of positive irrational beliefs (e.g., positive illusions) has been controversial in the scientific community. In addition to being recorded as symptoms by dominant psychiatry, positive

irrational beliefs are occasionally associated with subjective well-being. The correlation does not appear to be strong but is worth further investigation (Collard et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

The initial aim of this review was to find the individual and social predictors of irrational beliefs and behaviours. Important individual factors emerged, but insufficient social ones were found. In addition, we found a plethora of findings linking irrational beliefs (and much fewer behaviours) to specific mental disorders.

Regarding the latter finding, most studies show a significant link between irrational beliefs and mental disorders, but it is impossible to know whether irrational beliefs are the cause or effect of mental disorder. As stated in most studies, we can assume that irrational beliefs are the cause or one of the causes of mental disorders. On the contrary, mental illnesses can be considered predictors of irrational beliefs, but this possibility needs to be further investigated. In addition, we can point out that in certain mental states such as e.g. Addictions, irrational beliefs and behaviours are more often presented as possible causes, although of course, they could also be a result. The work has highlighted some personality traits that seem to be systematically linked to or shaped by irrational beliefs, such as anger, hostility, and demandingness (e.g., Fives et al., 2011). What needs to be further explored is whether different irrational beliefs are associated with different personality traits or different forms of difficulties or disorders. Furthermore, the pivotal role of emotions and their association with irrational beliefs have been confirmed, although it is not clear whether emotion precedes or follows irrational belief (Bernard & Joyce, 1984; David et al., 2010; Fives et al., 2011; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

It is important to note the potentially positive role of irrational beliefs in some cases. Further investigation of these cases and emphasis on subjective personal experiences will give us a better picture of the potential positive impact of some irrational beliefs (Collard et al., 2016). It is also worth dwelling on the slight reference to social predictors or social causes of irrational beliefs and behaviours. If, however, irrational beliefs are systematically linked to mental illness (e.g., Hyland et al., 2014; Jacoby et al., 2016), it seems, we cannot ignore the role of social causes, such as gender and socioeconomic status in the occurrence of mental disorders. We have seen the intercultural power of the relationship between irrational beliefs and psychological discomfort. This element is important in terms of psychological causes; however, possible intercultural differences could be studied in more detail. It would also be interesting to study beliefs in societies where the rational-irrational dipole does not have as clear characteristics as in Western societies.

In conclusion, it seems that some personality traits and behaviours associated with irrational beliefs have emerged, and extensive mental health difficulties and disorders are systematically associated with irrational beliefs and behaviours. The possibility of certain social situations such as financial and health crises favouring the development of irrational beliefs and behaviours needs to be systematically investigated. In this context, it is important to develop methods to prevent and deal with irrational beliefs through existing cognitive behavioural therapies or contribute to fields such as positive psychology.

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